

Future Agriculture Policy in the UK – Do all roads lead to Rome?

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As part of the protracted discussions on post-CAP agricultural support, keeping an eye on developments across other UK administrations is important. Whilst we do have autonomy to choose our own pathway we still need to operate under 'rules of the game' – be they from the World Trade Organisation, or HM Treasury, or embedded in the forthcoming UK Agricultural Support Framework or the Subsidy Control Bill. A recent conference hosted by Defra and the Agricultural Economics Society brought the contrasting approaches of the devolved administrations into stark focus. Not only are the approaches to agricultural policy divergent, the pace of change and amount of progress made to-date differs significantly.

So what has this got to do with roads to Rome? Each of the administrations are trying to achieve the same end-game – an agricultural / land management sector that is more environmentally sustainable. On that it is clear – words relating to farming resilience, productivity, biodiversity, woodlands, landscapes, public goods, ecosystem services, climate change, etc. abound in the agricultural policy discourse across the four administrations. Essentially all administrations are on the same journey – except the chosen routes are different.

The route the Welsh Government is taking has had a few changes already, with three consultations in less than two years. They aim to focus on consolidated environmental standards (e.g. for soil quality), enhanced woodland management and extent, and habitat and nutrient management. The Welsh Government are not scared to take difficult decisions, as witnessed by the decision to make the whole country an NVZ and the associated implications for livestock farmers – I suppose in a similar fashion to the Water Environment (Controlled Activities) (Scotland) Amendment Regulations 2021 that will have undoubted consequences for suckler producers. The Welsh Government have, however, acknowledged the need to get agricultural policy right and therefore have chosen to slow the transition journey down and, similarly to Scotland, are now not committed to any real change until 2025 (when some English farmers will have lost more than 50% of their direct support).

Defra appear to be further down the policy reform track in England compared to other administrations. They are on a different trajectory (although similar to that chosen by Welsh officials) and moving apace but their chosen route has already started to appear bumpy (as is often the case for innovators). Firstly, the recent report from the Public Accounts Committee at Westminster was somewhat damning of Defra's implementation strategy. The Committee acknowledged that the new Environmental Land Management scheme is an opportunity to press a reset button and focus on sustainable and productive agriculture sector. However, the Committee were critical of the lack of focus on the details of 'how' schemes can be delivered, and whether proposed schemes can offset the negative impacts on farm incomes that reductions in direct support are having. The Committee criticised the lack of a robust baseline, or metrics with which to measure

success, and (importantly) 'value for money'. Defra conceded to the Committee that "its confidence in the scheme looks like blind optimism without the details of what it has planned." Given this, it is therefore perhaps of little surprise that there are already reports emerging of concerns that the Rural Payment Agency are struggling to deliver the pilot schemes due to mapping and data issues – something farmers would have justifiably thought were a legacy of the CAP given the political rhetoric on 'simplification'.

Northern Ireland appear to be on a totally different route to England – and indeed appear to be pretty closely aligned to Scotland in terms of priorities, especially relating to farm incomes and food production. They have stolen a march on other administrations and produced very detailed, pretty solid proposals. DAERA aim to maintain some form of area based support payment to provide resilience support to farmers (with progressive top-slicing of amounts over £60,000). This safety net approach will stretch farmers to operate profitably or for them to enter environmental schemes to generate a living from farming. A declining share of this resilience budget will give their farmers time to adjust and adapt to new, more environmentally focused, schemes.

Perhaps most surprisingly for those that have not been following NI policy developments is the proposals to introduce a 'Headage Sustainability Package' for the suckler / finishing herds. DAERA aim to utilise the full 17% of their budget that the Northern Ireland Protocol permits them to spend on headage (non WTO 'green box' measures). This is not a simple win for suckler producers as they will have to deliver on performance – akin to the proposals set out by the Suckler Beef Climate Group co-chaired by Jim Walker here. Headage support is proposed to be conditional on farms: (i) reducing the age of first calving (max 27 months by year 4); (ii) reducing the calving interval (370 days by year 4); and (iii) achieving 24 month maximum age of prime cattle at slaughter by year 4.

DAERA's Farming for Nature Scheme will see its share of the budget grow over time to help maintain the natural environment (similar to AECS), and their additional Farming for Carbon scheme will support farmers to reduce their carbon footprints – again this echoes thinking in Scotland with an initial phase of baselining and testing before more concerted focus on delivering against targets. Equally there are similarities to our suggestions for the need for "transformational support" with the DAERA proposals (also present in England and Wales) aiming to introduce capital grants to support the required productivity / environmental changes that are supported by a knowledge exchange programme, a generational renewal (new entrant) programme and supply chain measures to strengthen farming's position in the food chain. The final part of the DAERA jigsaw is a crisis framework that will enable them to deal with, for example public intervention and private storage through top-slicing of support where required (e.g. in order to deal with issues such as the ongoing pig sector crisis).

Whilst Scotland now appears to be further behind along the policy evolution pathway than the rest of the UK, the Scottish Government are doing things differently here. The Farmer Led Group, co-design, approach inevitably will take longer to reach consensus than the top-down approach taken by other administrations. Will all roads lead to Rome and the 4 regions deliver the same outcomes? Definitely not – unless the introduced UK Agricultural Support Framework and the Subsidy Control Bill enforce a change of tack. Is that a bad thing? No – as we already deliver agricultural support differently, with different priorities and outcomes. As I have said before, the future's not what it used to be – there is a now undeniable acceptance that agricultural support policies must evolve significantly to deliver against contemporary environmental and societal challenges and

provide perceived value for money to taxpayers. How far we go, and what we are willing to sacrifice in order to get there is going to differ across the UK administrations. As they say 'the devil is in the detail' – but unfortunately there is still limited detail available yet from which to inform opinions.